

YOUTH OF UZBEKISTAN

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591509>

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Anntation: *The report "Youth of Uzbekistan: Problems and Prospects" covers the main aspects of life of young people in Uzbekistan - education and upbringing, professional life and economic opportunities, digital life and the Internet,*

Keywords : *information on the general situation of young people in the field of family and civic activities.*

"This new report, which brings together the voices of young people who make up the bulk of the population, reminds us of our duty to them. It is our duty to prepare young people for life in a world that represents the difference between employment, poverty and prosperity, despair and hope, "said Munir Mamedzade, UNICEF Representative in Uzbekistan. It is important to justify the confidence of today's youth, who make up the largest part of the population in the history of Uzbekistan, in achieving the goals of the program. "

According to the survey, the main concerns of young people are education (77% of respondents) and employment (61.8% of respondents). The report found that the majority of young people (54.6%) do not study, work or undergo vocational training after completing compulsory secondary education. This figure increases sharply for women over 18 years of age and is 74% for women aged 25-30 years. For men, the figure is lower, decreasing to 24.8% as they age.

The report also outlines the skills and knowledge that young people value most. These include knowledge of foreign languages, business literacy, and entrepreneurial skills. Young people also emphasized the need for "social" skills such as leadership and flexibility.

Gender inequality is also observed in the use of the Internet and knowledge of information technology. The number of young women (68.1%) who never use the Internet is twice as high as that of men (34.3%). The report notes that girls and young women are often criticized for using the Internet, and that the idea that the Internet has a negative impact on their behavior is widespread.

- rounded, purposeful and energetic young people with modern knowledge and skills, who can take responsibility for a decent future of the country, is the most

important condition for the sustainable and rapid development of the country. Ensuring the legitimate rights and interests of young people is one of the priorities of state policy , "said Bobur Bekmurodov, chairman of the Yuksalish national movement.

Based on the data analysis, the report makes recommendations aimed at improving the vital, technical, innovative and entrepreneurial skills of young people. One of the key recommendations is to ensure the active participation of young women in economic, social and political life by creating equal opportunities and encouraging behavioral change.

Distance education is not recognized in Uzbekistan . Problems of young people studying in universities of neighboring countries

the start of the new academic year, many applicants who were not able to enroll in Uzbek universities have gone abroad, mainly to study in neighboring countries.

The main applications come from graduates of universities in neighboring countries

to the State Inspectorate for Quality Control in Education , according to the statistics for 8 months of 2019, the largest number of applications for recognition of documents on foreign education came from graduates of education in the Kyrgyz Republic. (45.7 percent). The second place was taken by Tajikistan (16.7%), followed by Russia (14.3%) and Kazakhstan (10.6%).

These statistics apply not only to graduates of higher education, but also to the recognition of school, college-lyceum graduation documents.

most educators are applicants for documents on the recognition of foreign education (1216), many graduates in engineering, processing, construction, health, law." It was difficult for me to pass the entrance exams "

" Last year I entered the full-time department of one of the private universities in Almaty without entrance exams. I chose that university, despite the fact that it is non-governmental, thinking that it will be difficult for me to pass the entrance exams in Uzbekistan. However, the diploma of this university is not directly recognized by us. That's why I moved to Karaganda State Technical University. This university is included in the top thousand,"said one of the students , Boriboy Jumakulov.

According to him, the contract fee of the university where he is studying is 7 million (300 thousand tenge), and scholarships are not given to those who study on a contract basis. The cost per student can be as high as \$ 100 per month when used sparingly.

to accept the desire for higher education "

, head of the State Inspectorate for Quality Control in Education under the Cabinet of Ministers, explains why the majority of young people seeking higher education choose universities in neighboring Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan, rather than prestigious foreign universities. expressed his views.

In accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 "On measures to radically improve the system of spiritual and educational work" Vice-Rector for Youth and Spiritual and Enlightenment "Was introduced.

In order to further improve and increase the effectiveness of the educational process at the Institute, the main tasks of the Vice-Rector for Youth and Spiritual Enlightenment are to lead the spiritual and educational system, improve the work in this area, Preparation and publication of necessary scientific and methodological literature using experience, organization of training of staff in all fields, organization of meetings of various clubs, sports and public clubs, a broad explanation of respect for students, universal values, historical traditions, love, devotion to the ideas of independence, success in the spiritual sphere, training of qualified specialists, formation of personnel meeting new modern requirements, upbringing of loyal, spiritually and physically harmoniously developed youth.

Public organizations play a special role in the implementation of youth policy at the Institute . The activities of public organizations with the requirements are coordinated by the Department of Youth Affairs, Spirituality and Enlightenment of the Institute . Today, the primary organization of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan, the institute's women's adviser, head coach, psychologist, pedagogical educators of student dormitories work at the institute.

THE MAIN OBJECTIVE OF THE PROSECUTOR FOR YOUTH AFFAIRS AND SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL AFFAIRS:

- Carrying out organizational work on the implementation of the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Resolutions and Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, resolutions of the Oliy Majlis and the Cabinet of Ministers in the field of education and training;
- Ensuring the organization of spiritual and educational work and assistance in the training of qualified personnel;
- Organize the implementation of orders and instructions of ministries and higher organizations, decisions of the Academic Council of the Institute, as well as orders of the Institute on spiritual, educational and youth education;
- Organization of spiritual and educational work and training of qualified personnel on the basis of state educational standards;
- Ensuring that all deans and departments, heads of departments and teachers are fully aware of the content of knowledge and the set of requirements for the level of training in accordance with state educational standards;

- Organize the implementation of orders, directives and instructions of higher authorities, decisions of the Academic Council of the Institute and the rector's orders on issues of spiritual-educational and educational processes;
- Develop tools to study the development trends of the education system in developed countries, the Law "On Education", the "National Training Program" and other laws related to education. exit and ensure their implementation;
- Preparation of proposals and organization of work in the field of activity ;
- Coordination, organization and control of the work of departments, deans ' offices, providing spiritual-educational and educational process ;
- Approval of work plans of departments, faculties and departments and control over their implementation;
- control and ensure the implementation of paragraph 5 of the personal plan of professors and teachers;
- organization of conferences, meetings, round tables and conferences in the field of spirituality and enlightenment,
- Manage and assist in the process of searching for, selecting and working with talented young people, the process of preparing prestigious scholarship winners of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Navoi, Beruni, Ulugbek, Zulfiya and others among students and interns. compromise;
- Development of proposals for the staff of professors and teaching assistants, the organization of work to provide departments and divisions with qualified personnel ;
- Take action against employees who violate executive discipline , prepare proposals for termination of the contract with them;
- Conducting annual reports, analysis and conclusions of departments, faculties and departments, the implementation of modern methods of assessing the spiritual and educational activities of teachers;
- Carrying out regular spiritual and educational cooperation with institutes, ensuring the active participation of professors and teachers in conferences, seminars, cooperation with local authorities;
- Regular internal certification of the Institute in the prescribed manner, active participation in the preparation and conduct of external certification.
- The Institute should always ensure the role of young people in society, further increase their political and legal knowledge, fight against corruption, drug addiction, AIDS, terrorism, extremism, prevention of alcoholism and other negative evils;